

Małgorzata Dancewicz-Pawlik

ORCID: 0000-0003-4753-3464

University of Wrocław

Carbon footprint, monopoly, and potentiality of change: Tokenizing art as an aesthetic practice for alternative ecologies^{*}

Abstract: The article discusses certain aspects of blockchain-based art, including the ecology and economy of non-fungible tokens (NFTs), applying projects curated by Ruangrupa for documenta 15, such as *Jalar*, *Dayra*, *Cheesecoin*, and *BeeCoin*, created within the *lumbung* Economy. In light of earlier investigations into the ecology of NFTs, the main areas of concern now are the ways in which information about the environmental effects of NFTs presents itself, the monopolization of particular technological mechanisms, the perpetuation of cultural biases, and, from this angle, the belief of artists in the potential for change brought about by the new technology. Given the economic and ecological implications arising from the blockchain projects discussed in this article, I propose to use the notion of ecosophy defined by Félix Guattari as an approach for *lumbung* Economy interpretation.

Keywords: non-fungible tokens, documenta 15, ecosophy, *lumbung* Economy, economy and ecology of blockchain

Transversality of non-fungible token

One of the most significant parts of NFT art investigation is how new media art reframes the field of economic speculation in favour of an ecologically conscious, sustainable approach to art. As a starting point for analyzing this issue, I chose

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the NFT artwork projects presented at the last documenta, led by the Indonesian Ruangrupa,¹ which, under the call sign of “*lumbung* Economy,” brought together several pro-environmental projects related to blockchain and cryptocurrencies: *Jalar* (developed by Gudskul), *Dayra* (The Question of Funding), *Cheesecoin* (INLAND), and *BeeCoin* (developed by the ZK/U—Centre for Art and Urbanistics). After Félix Guattari, I will enable them ecospherical examples for the potentiality of change in contemporary art. The notion of ecosophy² was proposed by Guattari in *The Three Ecologies* and *Chaosmosis*.³ The concept incorporates an ecologically philosophical perspective on the following three areas: environment, social relations, and human subjectivity. From an economic and political standpoint, this approach offers a Guattarian paradigm of Integrated World Capitalism (IWC), with all of its hidden but ubiquitous effects. Establishing modest collaborative projects that are vulnerable to the chaos of shared subjectivities is the way to counteract this capitalist power. According to this viewpoint, the Ruangrupa’s *lumbung* concept meets all aspects of ecosophy.

Ruangrupa, in initiating the project, referred themselves to the concepts of Felix Guattari and Gilles Deleuze, characterizing their curating practices as a communal, rhizomatic, non-hierarchical, and fairly distributed method of producing art. However, invoking the concept of rhizome, they did not refer to Deleuze’s or Guattari’s concepts, as critics emphasize.⁴ By taking an ecospherical perspective, it is possible to focus on three areas: the social, mental, and environmental ecology of the *lumbung* project. This approach refers not only to art, but to the entire realm of media function daily and highlights the ecological and economic effects of blockchain technology. A transversal approach is assumed in the simultaneous investigation of the social, mental, and environmental domains. The concept of Guattarian transversality functions within ecosophy as a break with hierarchy, dualism, and boundaries between disciplines and can be realized in the communication of children, madmen, and in art. Due to the ethical and political implications, it corresponds well with the *lumbung* idea of making art as a way of common creation. However, this is inherent not only in the idea of Ruangrupa, but in the idea of NFT itself. NFT,

¹ Documenta 15, “Ruangrupa selected as artistic direction of documenta fifteen,” February 22, 2019, <https://documenta-fifteen.de/en/press-releases/ruangrupa-selected-as-artistic-direction-of-documenta-fifteen/> (accessed: 23.02.2025).

² About Guattari’s notion of *ecosophy* see: in Polish A. Ubertowska, “Ekozofie Guattarięgo,” *Przegląd Kulturoznawczy* 52, 2022, no. 2, pp. 212–221; in English M. Antonioli, “What is ecosophy?,” [in:] *Schizoanalysis and Ecosophy: Reading Deleuze and Guattari*, ed. C.V. Boundas, London 2017, pp. 74–86.

³ F. Guattari, *The Three Ecologies*, transl. I. Pindar, P. Sutton, London 2000; F. Guattari, *Chaosmosis: An Ethico-Aesthetic Paradigm*, transl. P. Bains, J. Pefanis, Bloomington 1995.

⁴ C.T. Yalçınkaya, “‘Making friends’ as labour: The political economy of the *lumbung* in documenta fifteen,” *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Art* 24, 2024, no. 1, pp. 62–85, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14434318.2024.2360556>.

seen as a new medium of expression in digital art and culture, is based on peer-to-peer technology, with decentralization and openness being its most distinctive features.

The terms *crypto art* or *NFT art* refer to both popular 8-bit images produced in NFTs and subversive art projects that apply the same technology. NFT is a highly transversal phenomenon. As a new actor on the stage of digital cultures, it performs various functions: social, aesthetic, didactic, economic, ludic, and even charitable. Formally, it is both a medium and information, both a material and a distribution platform. In the area of dissemination, it involves the artist, the institution (although it's a peer-to-peer system), the recipient and the buyer who, by making a purchase, becomes an art collector at the same time. Therefore, in a sense, NFT is a capacious and inclusive type of art. It is also one of the highly discussed phenomena in contemporary art and polarizes public opinion, as well as experts, who balance between the range of understanding of the concepts as: "harmful to the environment" and "lucrative for the artist." For establishing ownership and validity, it is kept on a blockchain. Because the ownership of each one is recorded in the blockchain and transferable by the owner, it cannot be copied, altered, or divided but can be bought, sold, or traded. To be able to code, one needs to have certain expertise, but minting or trading NFTs is accessible to anyone.

An NFT is a type of digital item or identification that may be applied to any kind of content, be it text, audio, video, memes, tickets, collector's objects, or artworks. It can be sports cards, venues, online meetings, club access, virtual plots, or apartments, all that can be digitized. Prior to the invention of NFTs, digital art began with reality, and digitality was the referent of reality. The opposite can be said in the case of NFTs, whose ontology is digital. They do not have their own referent, they have no concept of representing a material entity or event; they are self-referential, recursive, because they refer to themselves in creating meanings, highlighting the balance between what is virtual and what is real.

However conceptual and digitally purist any example of NFT design may be, minting art and distributing it via cryptocurrencies can be harmful to the environment. The relationship between the development of digital technology and climate change was made apparent by the arrival of Web 3.0 and blockchain technologies. Various environmental approaches to the topic are currently represented using the different technologies. Proof-of-work and proof-of-stake are becoming much more important in discussions about the phenomenon. Each of these technologies involves a different type of cryptocurrency. The fact of the interdependence of economy and ecology will be very important when it comes to *lumbung* at documenta, because all projects implemented within the *lumbung* Economy by Ruangrupa proposed environmentally friendly, anti-monopoly, transversal solutions regarding blockchain technologies and its currencies.

Ethereum's monopoly

NFT is based on blockchain technology, which has been improved and changed several times,⁵ while the breakthrough came on November 9, 2008, when Satoshi Nakamoto, in a white paper, announced the Bitcoin system. On January 3, 2009, the public Bitcoin network was launched, and the first block was issued.⁶ The first created NFT was the video *Quantum* by Jennifer and Kevin McCoy and Anil Dash, coded in 2014 and enabled by Namecoin,⁷ which is a fork of Bitcoin and was sold by McCoy to Dash for \$4 during a live presentation at the Seven on Seven conference at the New Museum in New York.

The hype on NFT, however, started with Ethereum, launched by Vitalik Buterin and Gavin Wood one year later. In the public consciousness, NFT got a lot of attention when *Everydays: The First 5,000 Days* by Mike Winkelmann, aka Beeple, was sold by Christie's in 2021. It was the first Ethereum-minted NFT sold in an auction house. The work presents graphics from 5,000 days of Winkelmann's daily activities.⁸ Ethereum started a process of becoming the most prominent cryptocurrency for NFT.

One of the first popular NFTs on Ethereum was CryptoPunks, developed by Matt Hall and John Watkinson. It is a collection of characters with distinctive traits, inspired by the cyberpunk movement.⁹ The project built on a similar idea is the Ethereum Bored Ape Yacht Club,¹⁰ created by Yuga Labs. Apes are procedurally generated by an algorithm. Owners of Bored Ape NFTs are given access to a closed online community, the Yacht Club, and ownership of the image's intellectual property. CryptoKitties¹¹ created by the Canadian company Dapper Labs, proposed virtual cats that could be bred and procreate families. They have a 256-bit separate genome that contains DNA. The offspring might inherit several characteristics from the parents. The Ethereum network was overloaded by the game's popularity in December 2017, which led to an all-time

⁵ This technology was first described as blockchain technology by Stuart Haber and W. Scott Stornett in 1991 (concerned with timestamping documents). Their system used cryptographically secured chains of blocks to store timestamped documents. See: S. Haber, W.S. Stornetta, "How to timestamp a digital document," *Journal of Cryptology* 3, 1991, no. 2, pp. 99–111, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00196791>.

⁶ S. Nakamoto, "Bitcoin: A peer-to-peer electronic cash system," Bitcoin.org, <https://bitcoin.org/bitcoin.pdf> (accessed: 6.09.2023).

⁷ J. McCoy, K. McCoy, *Quantum*, McCoy Space, <https://www.mccoyspace.com/project/125/> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

⁸ Beeple, <https://www.beeple-crap.com/> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

⁹ *CryptoPunk 5992*, CryptoPunks, <https://cryptopunks.app/cryptopunks/details/5992> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

¹⁰ Bored Ape Yacht Club, <https://boredapeyachtclub.com/#/> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

¹¹ CryptoKitties, <https://www.cryptokitties.co/> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

high in the number of transactions and to the high energy fees that players had to pay, causing a considerable slowdown.¹²

One of the first blockchain-based digital pet community games employing NFTs and the play-to-earn idea to be set in the metaverse was Axie Infinity.¹³ Axie players earn tokens by participating in turn-based battles against other players or computer-controlled teams. These tokens are then used to “breed” new monsters by creating more NFTs. Axie was developed by the Vietnamese studio Sky Mavis and minted in Ronin, an Ethereum fork.

Numerous further initiatives, while generating economic value, which is the primary determinant of NFTs, have a theoretical and critical component that is viewed as contributing to their status. NFT Archaeology is a continuation of the project that started in 1996 by Fred Forest when he auctioned an envelope with a secret code allowing the buyer to access his work *Parcelle / Réseau*¹⁴ online. In 2021 he modified and sold it on the blockchain for \$69.3 million + \$1. In *I’m a Coin*, Kevin Abosch¹⁵ stamped six vials of his blood on 100 pieces of paper, with codes that depicted the addresses of Ethereum. The work was a synthesis of his physical body, virtual work, and its monetary value. Damien Hirst in *The Currency*¹⁶ gave collectors one year to decide between 10,000 digital or physical artworks. Every time a physical work of dotted graphics is sold, the NFT is destroyed. All unpurchased NFTs will be destroyed after the end of the campaign, creating a balance between virtual and physical artwork. The project was supposed to end in 2022, but it was extended and continues to this day.

There are also numerous platform solutions available. TAEX was launched as a platform that leverages Tezos,¹⁷ which is regarded as more environmentally friendly than Ethereum. Here are some of the works accessible in DAI, a stable-coin based on the Ethereum blockchain that seeks to maintain a stable value of one dollar. If we look at the mint system in detail, we will notice that Ethereum owns the majority of the crypto market, which indicates a strong monopoly symptom. As such, the oppositional role of monopoly and peer-to-peer philosophy in forming the NFT ontology is noteworthy, influencing both commercial projects and those articulated in critical art.

¹² M.S. Smith, “The spectacular collapse of CryptoKitties, the first big blockchain game,” IEEE Spectrum, August 10, 2022, <https://spectrum.ieee.org/cryptokitties> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

¹³ Axie Infinity, <https://axieinfinity.com/> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

¹⁴ NFT Archeology, <https://nft-archeology.org/> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

¹⁵ K. Abosch, *I Am a Coin*, <https://www.iamacoin.com/> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

¹⁶ “Damien Hirst—*The Currency*,” OpenSea, July 2021, <https://opensea.io/collection/thecurrency> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

¹⁷ S. Negi, “TAEX features legendary artist Manovich in the latest NFT drop,” TechBullion, November 9, 2022, <https://techbullion.com/the-art-exchangetaex-features-legendary-artist-manovich-in-the-latest-nft-drop/> (accessed: 11.08.2023).

Merge footprint

On September 15, 2022, Ethereum transition its technology mechanism from proof-of-work (PoW) to proof-of-stake (PoS) in an event called The Merge. It is estimated to reduce energy consumption by 99.95%. The issue of energy production and its contribution to global warming is one of the main ethical concerns in the context of NFTs. PAK's The Merge collection honours the Ethereum Merge,¹⁸ a pivotal moment in the history of Ethereum that marked the completion of the network's switch from a PoW to a PoS consensus mechanism.¹⁹ Customers could purchase "mass units" rather than individual copies of an NFT edition of *Merge*.²⁰ The more mass purchasing, the greater the potential to "evolve" the artwork and the greater its value. A total of 312,686 mass units were sold to 28,983 customers, what is approximately \$91.8 million, the most expensive work of a living artist ever sold, but—what must be noted—sold to many customers.²¹

A PoW is a process for reaching consensus, it is difficult and requires a lot of computing effort from a network of devices, it is challenging to create, expensive, and time-consuming, yet straightforward for others to check and satisfies specific requirements. A PoS was created as an alternative to PoW. In the PoS consensus mechanism participants are selected based on their stake, the number of tokens they own. Since making a PoW might be a random process with low probability, it can take a lot of trial and error before a valid PoW is created. In PoW, block creators called miners must have energy-efficient computer equipment, and for their computational power they receive block rewards. Both mechanisms help blockchains synchronize data, validate information, and process transactions. The difference with PoS is that here participants, called validators, must own coins or tokens to confirm a consensus for the transaction. Validators share their resources and for this sharing, as a reward for validating, they receive a transactions fee. It is very energy efficient.²²

The Swiss company, Ethereum Switzerland GmbH (EthSuisse), the author of the software development, wants to be transparent. On their site, they post information on energy consumption and the carbon footprint that the algorithm produces. A comparison of the early PoW and PoS network can be found at the Cambridge Blockchain Network Sustainability Index,²³ where the data is provided

¹⁸ "Merge by Pak," Nifty Gateway Studio, December 3, 2021, <https://www.niftygateway.com/collections/pakmerge> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

¹⁹ P. Compare, "The Merge NFT: Ethereum collection that raised \$90,000,000+," CoinCodex, February 21, 2024, <https://coincodex.com/article/24706/the-merge-nft/> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

²⁰ "Merge by Pak."

²¹ J. Wallace, "The Merge: An NFT by Pak," Coin FOMO, <https://coinfomo.com/merge-nft-by-pak/> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

²² "What does proof-of-stake (PoS) mean in crypto?," Investopedia, June 13, 2024, <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/p/proof-stake-pos.asp> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

²³ "The Cambridge Blockchain Network Sustainability Index," The Cambridge Centre for Alternative Finance, <https://ccaf.io/cbnsi/ethereum> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

by the Crypto Carbon Ratings Institute (CCRI). The Institute's research proves that the annual energy consumption of Ethereum (ETH) is incomparably less compared to the energy production of Bitcoin (BTC) PoW, gaming in the US, Netflix, and even PayPal.²⁴ Cryptocurrencies that use the PoS validation system include Algorand, Avalanche, Cardano, EOS.IO, Gridcoin, Kin, Nxt, Peercoin, Polkadot, Solana, Steem, Tezos, TRON, and Ethereum (2.0), with Ethereum being the most approved and prominent.

Data visualization made by the Cambridge Blockchain Sustainability Index shows ETH energy consumption before and after The Merge, which is comparable to a swimming pool filled with water and a lemonade dispenser. The European Union is involved in blockchain development planning and proposes solutions that will introduce activities to monitor and shape blockchain technology concerning climate change, the most important of which is carbon footprint correction, while also supporting digital innovations to enable climate actions such as green technology and financing climate-supportive actions. They include the possibility of introducing a Central Bank Digital Currency to the EU market.²⁵

Numerous discussions started in reaction to these threads and arguments. In December 2020, media artist Memo Akten²⁶ launched the site CryptoArt.wtf, with the goal to disseminate the most accurate data on the energy consumption and environmental effects of the expanding PoW based crypto art and NFT marketplaces. Memo Akten's research project was initiated in December 2020 with the text "The unreasonable ecological cost of #cryptoart," that appeared on medium.com. The site was shut down by him due to too many controversies and conflicting opinions about the impact of NFT on the environment.²⁷

The manifesto entitled "Toward a new ecology of crypto art: A hybrid manifesto" posted on *Flash Art* website, was one of the outcomes of this conversation.²⁸ The discussion revolved around the neo-libertarian myth of artists' independence from galleries and art dealers, and the issue of NFT ontology as replicating the very system it was intended to disrupt.²⁹

In the manifesto, we can read that the art market is one of the most concentrated markets in the world. There is a small number of artists who have access

²⁴ "Ethereum's energy expenditure," Ethereum, October 24, 2023, <https://ethereum.org/en/energy-consumption> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

²⁵ "Blockchain for climate action," European Commission, October 25, 2024, <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/blockchain-climate-action> (accessed: 8.09.2023).

²⁶ Memo, <https://www.memo.tv/> (accessed: 2.09.2023).

²⁷ CryptoArt.wtf, <https://cryptoart.wtf/> (accessed: 2.09.2023).

²⁸ "Episode V. Toward a new ecology of crypto art: A hybrid manifesto," *Flash Art*, February 26, 2021, <https://flash---art.com/2021/02/episode-v-towards-a-new-ecology-of-crypto-art/> (accessed: 2.09.2023).

²⁹ It was published in *The Uncanny Valley*, a new digital column in *Flash Art*, and contributed by artists and theorists as Memo Akten, Jason Bailey, Alice Bucknell, Chloe Diamond, Primavera De Filippi, Fanny Lakoubay, Geert Lovink, Casey REAS.

to just a few high-profile institutions, exhibitions, and auctions.³⁰ The discourse on breaking away from the neocolonial image of the art world has been going on for a long time and is taking on completely new forms, particularly in the developing countries where blockchain miners are moving. Peter Howson³¹ states that the neocolonialism of blockchains lies in three approaches. Ongoing narratives of “green grabbing” liquidate local claims to resources for green investments. Inequalities in North-South trade and investment are sustained by the technology. An old/new power asymmetry is produced by the technology through data colonialism and surveillance capitalism.³² As Jason Bailey at The Uncanny Valley writes: “Regardless of artistic skill, most artists have no statistical chance of success in the traditional art market because of a combination of factors outside their control, namely gender, race, and geography.”³³ It is essential to consider how and whether it is possible to find a solution to change this mindset.

Lumbung ecosophy

Current critical and commercial NFT operations have a direct connection to the transition from potentially promising peer-to-peer concepts to monopoly capitalist techniques of selling NFTs. The documenta curators implied collaborative projects under the broad heading “*lumbung* Economy” as an answer to these challenges. In the introduction to *The Three Ecologies* more than three decades ago, Guattari wrote:

The Earth is undergoing a period of intense techno-scientific transformations. If no remedy is found, the ecological disequilibrium this has generated will ultimately threaten the continuation of life on the planet’s surface. Alongside these upheavals, human modes of life, both individual and collective, are progressively deteriorating. Kinship networks tend to be reduced to a bare minimum; domestic life is being poisoned by the gangrene of mass-media consumption; family and married life are frequently “ossified” by a sort of standardization of behaviour; and neighbourhood relations are generally reduced to their meanest expression.³⁴

This seems like the most recent quotation that functions as an overview of the *Lumbung* project. *Lumbung* means rice barn, a location to keep rice produced by the community as a shared resource for future use. It can also mean friendship, working well together, sharing things, and looking after everyone in a group. It was the main idea of the last documenta 15, curated by Jakarta-based

³⁰ “Episode V. Toward a new ecology of crypto art.”

³¹ P. Howson, “Climate crises and crypto-colonialism: Conjuring value on the blockchain frontiers of the global south,” *Frontiers* 3, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbloc.2020.00022>.

³² See also Michael Herzfeld, “The absence presence: Discourses of crypto-colonialism,” *The South Atlantic Quarterly* 101, 2002, no. 4, pp. 899–926, <https://muse.jhu.edu/article/39112/summary> (accessed: 2.09.2023).

³³ “Episode V. Toward a new ecology of crypto art.”

³⁴ F. Guattari, *The Three Ecologies*, p. 27.

collective Ruangrupa, and 14 groups of almost 1,500 artists from all over the world.³⁵ As they stated, “At the heart of documenta 15 is an exploration of economic experiments.”³⁶ In this practice, artists collectively ask what actions enable the development of a community-based arts economy founded on *lumbung* principles like humour, kindness, independence, openness, sufficiency, and regeneration. The creators of four projects based on blockchain ideas: *Jalar*, *Dayra*, *Cheesecoin*, and *BeeCoin*, attempted to provide a response to this question.³⁷ Ruangrupa writes in the documenta handbook that they discovered from the permanent employees who worked on earlier documenta iterations that the majority of the artworks on display are sold off-site by gallerists during the course of the exhibition’s 100 days and then delivered to collectors. To raise concerns about the economy, ownership, labour, and exchange a matter of culture, Ruangrupa decided to bring this to the forefront.³⁸ Remedy for this wide range of economic-political-social-individual problems caused by IWC is a new way of simultaneously applied, theoretical, ethical, political, and creative strategy called by Guattari ecosophy, which is “an ethico-political articulation between the three ecological registers: the environment, social relations and human subjectivity.”³⁹

Social ecology

Documenta 15 was a deeply transversal experience. Curators who were assigned to carry out the collective practices of the *lumbung* Economy had to decide how to represent the idea of value exchange—something that cannot be represented through visualization. Every project in the *lumbung* Economy referred to the emerging blockchain technologies and the concept of collective sharing. As a result, someone who attended documenta and might have expected to see technological objects shown as exhibition components, including different display devices or graphics processors, discovered something entirely unusual. During the visit to the exhibition, we mostly noticed spaces set aside for assemblies. According to the artists, these areas allowed people to meet in groups without any set agenda or time limit, exchange information and stories, and establish

³⁵ Documenta 15, “Lumbung,” <https://documenta-fifteen.de/en/easy-lumbung/> (accessed: 26.08.2023).

³⁶ Documenta 15, “*BeeCoin*, *Cheesecoin*, *Dayra* and *Jalar*: *Lumbung* currency at documenta fifteen,” August 18, 2022, <https://documenta-fifteen.de/en/press-releases/beecoin-cheesecoin-dayra-and-jalar-lumbung-currency-at-documenta-fifteen/> (accessed: 26.08.2023).

³⁷ Documenta 15, “*Lumbung* currency: Working group,” <https://documenta-fifteen.de/en/lumbung-currency/> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

³⁸ See K. Córdova, “Field notes: Kim Córdova on INLAND at documenta 15,” e-flux Education, July 26, 2022, <https://www.e-flux.com/announcements/481113/field-notes-kim-crdoва-on-inland-at-documenta-15/> (accessed: 23.02.2025); see also: Ruangrupa, “From mini to akbar: We are not in documenta fifteen, we are in *lumbung* one,” *Documenta 15 Handbook*, Ostfildern 2022, pp. 24–25.

³⁹ F. Guattari, *The Three Ecologies*, p. 28.

a place of refuge and shared moments. Slogan-filled large-format graphic manifestos served as illustrations for these concepts.

The main documenta exhibition area, Fridericianum, became, for the duration of documenta 15, the least connected piece of the white cube contemporary art world. The Fridericianum was transformed into a collective school, called Fridskul, where artists occupied the space for workshops and seminars, and were even eating and sleeping there together. For the 100 days of documenta, the host of Fridskul, the Gudskul collective,⁴⁰ turned some of the Fridericianum rooms into a kitchen and dormitory.⁴¹ Gudskul was responsible for many collective activities. One of them was *Temujalar*, a project⁴² for exchanging information in education. It was created in 2018 by the collectives Ruangrupa, Serrum, and Grafis Huru Hara, all of whom are based in Jakarta. They create an environment where numerous people work together. As we can read at the website of documenta 15,⁴³ *temu* and *jalar* are two Indonesian terms that mean to meet and disseminate.

Gudskul launched *Temujalar.art* in 2020, during the start of the COVID-19 pandemic. It is a website for collectives and their artistic ecosystems. The portal aims to support their learning, experience gathering, and knowledge sharing. Members of the *Temujalar.art*⁴⁴ project can earn and accumulate virtual currency known as Jalar for their Jalar Collective Wallet. By supplying the platform with resources or activities, they produce Jalar. They can use it to create a common area or to participate in online classes and events. For Gudskul, collaboration and sharing are two essential components of the growth of Indonesian modern art and culture.

The documenta 15 common pot, which was collectively administered by artist groups, is analogous to the Jalar Collective Wallet, also as a model of cryptocurrency. Social ecology, according to Guattari's theory of the three ecologies, is the mass movement of like-minded individuals producing subjectivities by the cooperative creation of shared concepts and values. "Social ecosophy will consist in developing specific practices that will modify and reinvent the ways in which we live,"⁴⁵ Guattari writes. It is founded on experimental methods that have the potential to reunite three previously divided elements: the mind, society, and the environment. The three ecologies and ecosophy notions apply to the *lumbung* Economy. Because *Temujalar* directly addresses social structures and how educational methods can influence them to change, it is most closely aligned with the concept of social ecology.

⁴⁰ Gudskul, "Sekolah Temujalar," <https://gudskul.art/sekolahtemujalar/> (accessed: 22.08.2024).

⁴¹ Documenta 15, "Fridericianum as a School: Fridskul," <https://documenta-fifteen.de/en/fridskul/> (accessed: 22.08.2024).

⁴² Gudskul, <https://gudskul.art/> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

⁴³ Documenta 15, "Gudskul," <https://documenta-fifteen.de/en/lumbung-members-artists/gudskul/> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

⁴⁴ Temujalar, <https://web.temujalar.art/> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

⁴⁵ F. Guattari, *The Three Ecologies*, p. 34.

Mental ecology

Mental ecology will compel us to reconsider how an individual engages with their body, phantasm, time passing, and the “mysteries” surrounding life and death. It will force us to seek solutions for a variety of issues, including fashion uniformity, the standardization of the mass media and telecommunications, and the manipulation of public opinion through advertisements and polls. It’s an internal struggle against the prejudices and biases that have been applied to societies and individuals in the process of mental development.

Among the initiatives that advances the concept of mental ecology was *Dayra*, invented by the member of the *lumbung* team, the Gaza artists group The Question of Funding and Kassel-based activist. The project was organized in the form of a website and publications on community economics and financing and was based on the model of cryptocurrency. In Arabic, the word *dayra* refers to both a circle and a revolving noun or verb. It helps communities to maintain its wealth by exchanging resources such as material, physical, or intellectual, and knowledge, especially in cases of lack of money. The scheme assumes no accumulation, only exchange.⁴⁶ It’s an economic system that uses blockchain technology to circulate shared values. It’s intended for individuals, small firms, and organizations that don’t have a lot of money but have other resources like expertise and material or physical goods. It allows the exchange of services, resources, and locations in exchange for cryptocurrencies.⁴⁷ Therefore, via the exchange and utilization of these non-monetary resources, currency facilitates value creation for the benefit of everybody.

Not only because of its innovative shared economy initiatives, but also because of the controversies surrounding the political participation of the collectives invited to build the *lumbung* Economy, documenta 15 came to attention. As for the activities of The Question of Funding and the anti-Semitism they were accused of, among other things, of inviting the Eltiqa group, who created the work *Guernica Gaza* (2022), to the exhibition. Perhaps this is why the ideas for *Dayra lumbung* were not developed here as they could have been.⁴⁸

⁴⁶ Dayra, “*Dayra*—how it works?,” Vimeo, https://vimeo.com/721710848?embedded=true&source=vimeo_logo&owner=178634131 (accessed: 29.09.2023).

⁴⁷ “*Dayra* or how to circulate communal economic value?,” Dayra.net, <https://dayra.net/#how> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

⁴⁸ For more information see K. Jhala, “Documenta drama: The six most controversial (and confusing) things we saw at the Kassel exhibition,” *The Art Newspaper*, June 21, 2022, <https://www.theartnewspaper.com/2022/06/21/documenta-15-most-controversial-kassel-exhibition>; see also: Documenta 15, “The Question of Funding,” <https://documenta-fifteen.de/en/lumbung-members-artists/the-question-of-funding/> and D. Genda, “The slow work of dialogue: an interview with The Question of Funding,” Berlin Art Link, July 22, 2022, <https://www.berlinartlink.com/2022/07/22/interview-with-question-of-funding/> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

Another project developed within the *lumbung* Economy, *Cheesecoin*,⁴⁹ was created as a fictional currency to support INLAND's activities. INLAND⁵⁰ is a collaborative project initiated in 2009 by Fernando García-Dory,⁵¹ which provides a forum for various actors involved in the production of agricultural, social, and cultural content. The initiative was started in association with Hito Steyerl, an artist who decided to remove the piece from the show because of disagreements over how documenta handled accusations of anti-Semitism, among other factors.⁵² *Cheesecoin* was an example of a nonlinear economy that could coexist with capitalist market economies. As a false currency, a limited-edition art and money form was distributed through networks of trade with regional farmers and through the dairy pavilion in the Ottoneum's garden. *Cheesecoin* represented the early stages of an experimental economy as it transitioned from being purely speculative to becoming real.

For the exhibition, INLAND created a kind of folk museum and a learning environment or expanded syllabus that gathered resources, current projects, and partnerships. Ottoneum's installation was like a museum of wonders filled with information on anything from farming and forest ecology to a sound anthropology of rural decline and healing.⁵³ The project's creators state that: "Instead of being a means of payment, *Cheesecoin* maps an 'internet of stink' that arises when fungi, moulds, and bacteria communicate with one another via smell. The result is partly cheese. [...] Technology is thus controlled by natural and social processes—not the other way around."⁵⁴

In the frame of documenta 15, the issues of controversy related to the political and historical aspects of numerous works revealed themselves. INLAND was also one of the main focuses of this conversation. Accusations of anti-Semitism included, foremost, the widely discussed in the media Taring Padi's *People's Justice* work. The activities of the collectives The Question of Funding and Archives des luttes des femmes en Algérie were also very controversial in the context of anti-Semitism. As a result of this controversy, Sabine Schormann, director of the documenta, and Meron Mendel, documenta advisor and director of the Anne Frank Education Centre, resigned, while Hito Steyerl withdrew her video work *Animal Spirits*, which had been produced in cooperation with *lumbung* currency

⁴⁹ Dokumenta 15, "BeeCoin, Cheesecoin, Dayra and Jalar."

⁵⁰ Inland—Art, Agriculture & Territory, <https://inland.org/> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

⁵¹ Fernando García-Dory, <https://www.fernandogarciadory.info/> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

⁵² Documenta 15, "Animal Spirits—cave art, mountain digital guerilla, and introduction to the *Cheesecoin* by INLAND," <https://documenta-fifteen.de/en/calendar/animal-spirits-cave-art-mountain-digital-guerilla-and-introduction-to-the-cheesecoin/> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

⁵³ "INLAND—Campo Adentro. Documenta fifteen," Inland—Art, Agriculture & Territory, <https://inland.org/nland-campo-adentro-documenta-fifteen/> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

⁵⁴ Ibid.

and arranged by INLAND.⁵⁵ Since such endeavours demonstrated how much work needs to be done to develop conscious subjectivity in the fields of art production, distribution, and reception, I proposed classifying these two collectives under the mental ecology category.

Environmental ecology

The amalgamation of anything natural, human, and machinic is described as environmental ecology. It can also be called machinic ecology since machines have always been at the centre of cosmic and human praxis. This profound notion of ecology is seen when analyzing the *BeeCoin* project. Invented by the ZK/U—Centre for Art and Urbanistics, it was the most visible during the event, taking up a large space in the ruruHaus in the centre of Kassel. The project's mission was to safeguard and enhance bees' well-being on a global scale, focusing on bees and urban society. The association, a group that makes decisions in routine assembly meetings, uses web3 technology and sensor kits that track the vital signs of more than 15 beehives in Kassel. The BeeDAO experiment functions as a Distributed Autonomous Organization (DAO) and is an example of how human and nonhuman agents might cooperate to achieve common objectives. To join BeeDAO and become a beeholder, bees and humans must either donate their data (proof-of-life) or sign up for an NFT membership. As part of the project, everyone could join the community, become a bee observer, an NFT donor, or an ordinary viewer of the exhibition, where in the ruruHaus we could see data visualization on three-dimensional models and charts of changing cryptocurrencies called the Moloch DAO—created to contribute to the development of ETH 2.0. *Lumbung* in documenta 15 took from blockchain technology and the metaphor of working as DAO, a member-owned organization with decentralized leadership, which means an organization whose voting and financial operations are conducted using a blockchain and which is run entirely or in part by decentralized computer programs. With a *lumbung* DAO, the abbreviation extension was The Digital Autonomous Organization (DAO) for the *BeeCoin*, and it was created by *lumbung* member ZK/U—Centre for Arts and Urbanistics with the help of Paul Seidler and Steph Holl-Trieu.⁵⁶ Curators used DAO to express a new economic model for financing and trading art. Inspiration came from algocracy, algorithmic regulation from a peer-to-peer management system. DAO is an organizational model whose voting and financial operations are conducted using a blockchain and

⁵⁵ For more information see A. Greenberger, "Documenta's anti-Semitism controversy, explained: How a German art show became the year's most contentious exhibition," *Art News*, July 22, 2022, <https://www.artnews.com/art-news/news/what-is-documenta-15-antisemitism-controversy-1234635001/> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

⁵⁶ Documenta 15, "*BeeCoin, Cheesecoin, Dayra and Jalar*."

which is run entirely or in part by decentralized computer programs. In general, it consists of member-owned organizations with decentralized leadership, but the question of its governance is very important, because they typically allocate and distribute voting tokens, so token accumulation can lead to the concentration of power. Documenta curators write on the homepage:

The learning sessions led into the existing currency plans of the *lumbung* members as described below. The processes of development of the currencies are partly on view in the exhibition in Kassel. After documenta 15, when the individual currencies have come to fuller life, the *lumbung* intends to work on ways of connecting the currencies to each other to enable value exchange between local communities outside of often inflexible and bureaucratic mainstream banking and accountability systems.⁵⁷

The idea of developing a system of governance and wealth-sharing between bees and humans was created in 2019 by the artist collective KUNSTrePUBLIK (Matthias Einhoff, Philip Horst, and Harry Sachs), the group behind ZK/U—Centre for Art and Urbanistics. The concept was created in relation to Haus der Statistik and ZK/U’s Statista Project Series, recalling the planned economic initiatives that were once carried out in this old GDR structure from the socialist modernist era. A preliminary version of BeeDAO was created as a decentralized, autonomous organization in collaboration with the art-tech pioneers Terra0 and the citizen-science group Hiveeyes. Taking advantage of documenta15, BeeDAO enters a second iteration and establishes the Beeholder community within it.⁵⁸ The nature of crypto art as ecologically relevant is examined here. Terra0, a project established in 2017 by Paul Seidler, Max Hampshire, and Paul Kolling that is closely related to *BeeCoin*, utilizes ecological and technological potential by making use of blockchain technology to support the growth and development of a forest by raising money through the sale of its own resource (wood) in order to increase its area through the acquisition of new property.⁵⁹ This mechanistic vision of an environmental ecology in which humans, as individuals and as collectives, nature, and technology mutually influence each other is particularly visible in *BeeCoin*.

Conclusion

In the introduction to the English edition of *The Three Ecologies*, the translators, citing Bateson, write: “an ecological struggle for survival is taking place in

⁵⁷ Documenta 15, “*Lumbung* currency.”

⁵⁸ *BeeDAO*, ZK/U, <https://beedao.zku-berlin.org/>; see also: The *BeeCoin* Project, <https://www.beecoin.de/>; The Hiveeyes Community, <https://community.hiveeyes.org/c/bee-observer/54>; “Statista Presentation Week programme,” September 11–16, 2019, <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ytE-vwaemdYJqJo3AziUQD32xjX7auPuzUOPGel3eVk/edit>; *Beeholder—BeeCoin*, ZK/U, <https://www.zku-berlin.org/projects/beeholder-beecoin/> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

⁵⁹ Terra0, <https://terra0.org/> (accessed: 2.09.2023); Flowertokens, <https://flowertokens.terra0.org/> (accessed: 2.09.2023).

the domain of ideas.”⁶⁰ Considering the nature of *lumbung* projects presented at documenta 15 and the fact that PoS technology was widely used by non-mainstream media artists long before ETH became famous for being green thanks to The Merge, the question arises: how does the mainstream use the ideas and mechanisms of the alternative, critical artists? Many distinct cryptocurrencies use PoS, but it was Ethereum (2.0) that was largely discussed in the media in the context of energy consumption and the change in the philosophy of minting to green. The Merge is part of a larger philosophical shift in the blockchain industry toward a more environmentally friendly approach, but why is the discussion centred on the most prominent technology,⁶¹ when there are numerous solutions of alternative economic models based on peer-to-peer models, even speculative and fictional? As the documenta curators propose about *lumbung* initiatives: “They act as concrete mechanisms to generate unrestricted resources for longer term *lumbung*-building—or, in other words, to transvers money from the classical exhibition economy towards the commons-based *lumbung* Economy.”⁶² The *lumbung* ecosystem is the term coined to describe the intention of working through art for collectivity, democratic principles, and sharing resources.⁶³ However, it seems more important to ask what metaphor the system for changing ETH from PoW to PoS can be. Let’s go back to the ETH Merge as it was crucial for the NFT development, as described by a large part of the industry media. The topic of how the mainstream employs the concepts and mechanisms of the alternative, critical art has been raising since another small PoS based cryptocurrency was widely used by non-mainstream media artists to mint before ETH gained popularity as an ecofriendly technology. Thus, an epistemological dilemma arises. Does this Merge approach change the mainstream and therefore the entire system of these relationships, having a positive impact not only on climate change? Or maybe these ideas are being absorbed by the mainstream, that operates under the guise of sustainable expansion in accordance with its constant norms established in the art world? Viewing *lumbung* economics as another The Merge promise, in fact impossible to operate and difficult to see from our Western art world perspective, could be assumed to be the answer. This is what the digital and non-digital contradiction of NFT in art makes us conceive. In the course of this profound ambiguity, one of the possible answers has historically been found throughout numerous emerging innovations that evolved over time. We remain far from ready in terms of consciousness to fully embrace a novel medium to which we must advance, and this process will be accomplished not by projecting predictions of the impact of technology in

⁶⁰ I. Pindar, P. Sutton, “Translators’ introduction,” [in:] F. Guattari, *The Three Ecologies*, p. 16.

⁶¹ Documenta 15, “*Lumbung* currency.”

⁶² Documenta 15, “*Lumbung* working groups—alternative economies and collective practice,” August 19, 2022, <https://documenta-fifteen.de/en/news/lumbung-working-groups-alternative-economies-and-collective-practice/> (accessed: 29.09.2023).

⁶³ Documenta 15, “Ruangrupa,” <https://documenta-fifteen.de/en/press-releases/ruangrupa-selected-as-artistic-direction-of-documenta-fifteen/> (accessed: 26.08.2023).

the future through futurology, but by performing an in-depth analysis of the relationship between the non-digital and digital realities of art, as well as examples of everyday life blockchain-based works. In *Chaosmosis*, Guattari proposed the notion of ecosophical objects to the idea of ecosophy. Four dimensions can define it: flow, machine, value, and existential territory. Guattari describes this idea as connecting the machines of the ecosystems of material flow with the ecosystems of semiotic flow. Ecosophical objects flow is characterized by autopoiesis, which is a feature of all systems, not only living ones. But it is also a bearer of values, registers, and perspectives of valorization, as Guattari states.⁶⁴ The problematization of value, including ecological as well as economical value, also in capitalistic understanding, is crucial for the idea of ecosophy. The valorization of ecosophical objects is done by means of autopoiesis in the sense of social, environmental, and mental aesthetics. Guattari states that ecosophical objects have their “existential territories,” founded in extrinsic, independent coordinates of determination. This means that they have a beginning and an end and are subject to evolution of self-conception in complexity. When considering the idea of ecosophy regarding NFT, we observe activities that are simultaneously individual and collective, egalitarian and capitalist, material and immaterial, in constant internal contradiction. These practices are also rapidly altering as new ones emerge in the field of the internet art. The crucial thing is to approach analysis from the three ecologies perspective, which calls for a redefining of social, mental, and environmental ecosophical relationships.

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⁶⁴ See F. Guattari “Qu’est ce que l’écophilosophie?” *Revue Critique d’Ecologie Politique* 21, 2006, <https://ecorev.org/spip.php?article 479> (accessed: 21.08.2024).

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Małgorzata Dancewicz-Pawlik, PhD—graduated from the Jagiellonian University’s Institute of Audiovisual Arts and received a doctorate in Cultural Studies from the University of Wrocław. She is the author of the monograph *Performans postmedialny. Współczesny kontekst technologiczny działań performatywnych* [Postmedia Performance: Contemporary Technological Context of Performative Actions] (Wrocław 2019). She experiments with audiovisual performance (www.inire.net) and curates performance projects (www.intermediale.com). Her research interests concentrate on numerous kinds of art and new technologies, as well as the interactions they create along the action–representation–aesthetic perception continuum.